

TRAINING TEACHERS IN FINLAND AND FIN EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. *In the article, the historical background of teacher education in Finland, the Finnish education system to itself, special features, teacher training, and now action-doing teachers of education study program and his main features and principles about data are covered in detail.*

Keywords: *International education, foreign experience, the Finnish education system, teacher education, training programs, science—the result*

Introduction. Intellectual activity of new teachers in the countries of the world, development, and improvement of personnel training systems are important professions that are going in our country, not only young people but perhaps the whole of our society's member's knowledge level increases; first of all, high spiritual development is defined as the main task. Perform these tasks in raising the teacher's pedagogical skills. Advanced experiences are important. Because teacher-knowledgeable personnel preparation, students different orientations to fields, implementation of reforms in continuous education processes, education of a new generation of strategic thinking, educated and qualified personnel, in-depth study of advanced experiences abroad, updating the educational process, teaching methodology, form, and methods to knowledge in application justification, such as done to increase in charge person, is considered, therefore, the world experience of learning and international education in the system, take-going reforms analysis, and reach current are considered.

Whole the world, teachers and politicians pay attention. We all know that education in the center is the Finnish education system. For more than a decade, Finnish 15-year-olds have consistently shown the best and highest results in the OECD international evaluation program (PISA). In three years, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development will transfer one transferable international student to research Finnish school students.

The world's highest knowledge level is sufficient demonstration. They are also children and the most avid book readers in the world. Also, Finnish school students in natural sciences, according to - in the world, second, mathematics according to, while fifth place takeover is coming.

Main part: Finland's education system for the most important period (1967–1974)

Between periods, in 1967, Finland was in the parliament before pushed suggestions to increase, and it has been. As a result, 11–12-year-old students study or professional education was "flow," which was transferred to comprehensive education; decision-making powers were not centralized. All teachers in universities (children from kindergarten except) requested to receive Providing schools with highly educated personnel is regular on the road. At the time, in Finland, general, professional, and higher education are given "free," and adult education is partially supported. According to the legislation, the teachers of the curriculum are local health care and social services responsibility-loaded offices, working in collaboration and taking into account "the school's working environment, local value choices, and special resources". received without work outputs is a must. She is not only "general of education

high standards, but also to the jointly defined goals and procedures of the whole society loyalty". provides way done is increased.

Educational system of Finland present structure as follows:

Primary education (ages 6 and under): All since 2001, families have been given the opportunity to study in pre-school educational institutions. As a result, approximately 96% of children go to preschool educational institutions. The pedagogues-teachers of the pre-school educational institution have to have at least a bachelor's degree level, which is a must.

General medium education school: "the main one education," that too is called, and the following stages, divided into: Primary stage (Grades 1-6): To the student's education to give for "class," who must have at least a master's degree in their specialty, "teachers" undertake is loaded. Lower secondary level (grades 7-9): Students have one or two subjects (as well as pedagogy) at least in the field of specialization. master level has to be needed was "science" teachers" lesson they give During basic education, all material resources—food and transport—are provided. Students from at least 9–12 classes for "vocational schools", the rest and medium schools they choose Senior High School (Grades 10–12): The student's higher (academic) education prepares At the end of secondary school, students in four subjects (the rest optional) submit the only official "exam" This will give them the right to study access certificate and higher education. Profession schools: high-medium education, such as general education schools accepts students and prepares them for work immediately after school. Other countries' professions from schools are different; they are basically "apprenticeship" statuses that will be organized. However, many students continue to enter higher educational institutions in the technical direction to get a degree they make. Teachers of vocational schools are in technical universities specialized in 'chase plan according to latest advancements are prepared.

According to the education and field of work of teachers in Finnish schools, teachers of preschool education and teachers of crafts and technology can be divided into music teachers and other categories. However, in each category, teachers prepare different study programs based on their main goal and objectives.

In 1970, "The teacher training" about "the law acceptance to be done with Finland education in success, mainly occupied with a big reforms which are done by increased methodology. For newly established general education schools and secondary schools, teachers' preparation for higher studies in their countries is also required. The majority of universities are divided into two departments: common scientific and science in the field education and pedagogical education directions. First: common scientific and science education in the field research take to go and in planning problems on work main direction as given if the second: pedagogical to education, i.e., teaching and teachers education in the field to research attention was directed.

The future of teachers begins with education, and all teachers are required to have general and broad skills. This is the science of pedagogy; it is necessary to develop that teachers are ready to become teachers, and their social-emotional growth contribution additions must Teachers own to work the most to research based on pedagogical, optimistic in relation to being, and theoretical and practical studies take to go. Also, study sciences and pedagogical sciences must be combined to be more successful. Teacher education from the study of society and education policy consists of:

1. Class teachers: This teacher provides general education in schools for lower classes.

2. (1-6) for being responsible. They are usually themselves engaged in the class, which teaches all subjects and is responsible for the "whole personal development" of students too. Students to class when rising teachers, they are with together

3. Movement they do Science teachers general education of schools high stages (7-9) and high medium in schools lessons they give They usually teach one or two disciplines according to their specialized areas.

4. Despite the following wide range of groups to which teachers can be trained:

5. Academic sciences;

6. Pedagogical studies;

7. Language and AKT studies;

8. Personal study plan;

9. Optional.

The following principles are for teacher training system:

1. Independence, responsibility, and trust. Finland pedagogical education is at the core of all level teachers, not only independent specialists, maybe "own there is a belief that one should be an expert in the fields" and it is different problems (pedagogical, administrative, related to family or community, even local industry with connections) independent respectively and own colleagues and local community with in collaboration the solution finds In the teacher this of virtues development, one from the side teaching profession in Finland the most a lot demand to be done and authoritative from professions to one turned if second from the side development of educational program and students to administrators and politicians which allows almost complete "handover" of assessment tasks to teachers trust basis organize did Teachers and school directors study, which plays a key role in the development of programs. Pedagogical education is their education program that provides well-developed knowledge and planning skills. In addition, the design of training program is a systematic, theoretical professional development in terms of improving the help given.

To research based on independence, responsibility and trust principle with dependent being serious to research based on the approach acceptance to do principle. Highlight the two main goals behind this principle is important. First, the future to teachers own activity in the field last to be aware of researches, as well as to add new knowledge will give. Also, the second biggest goal is teachers' own beliefs and practices about thought and skill development. The future science teachers are to research based on the pedagogical purpose of education: "To the teachers, independent thinking and making sense evidence through practice make it possible. There has been a problem. The solution to help give education is to give." Theory and practice according to Finnish methodology principle. The third determining principle of education is that theoretical aspects of the study process are practiced with strong integration.

Summary.

In conclusion, some of the current main features of Finnish education, the 1960s, the end, and in the 1970s, teachers in education reforms in Finland believed education development was the key. This from reforms one "standardized" tests void to do was Finn school's students success determination for standardized from the tests does not use Of these three main reasons, there are

Firstly, evaluation practice national o ' chase in the program good based on although in Finland education policy schools of activity important part as individual education and to creativity high priority will give. As a result, for each student's academic success, statistical

indicators are used to determine how far his individual development and ability have progressed. Second, the creators of education, curriculum, training, and certification not conducting tests in schools, but strengthening the practice of teachers; they emphasize that it is necessary. Assessment of students' knowledge in Finnish schools study program and study to the process included being whole study year during teachers and students improve performance for is used.

Thirdly, in Finland, the determination of students' academic indicators is considered the responsibility of the school and not of external evaluators. So, our country education in the system problems elimination for advanced national and foreign experiences, international evaluation program requirements in consideration received without o ‘ chase program, o ‘ school methodology and education quality evaluation system improvement, to teachers was confidence gain, of pedagogues own to work was responsibility increase very is important.

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